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NLRP12 expression is controlled by NOD2 and activated in cells and tissues of humans with Crohn's Disease.

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NLRP12 was expressed in the hematopoietic compartment in a stage selective manner in the myeloid lineage. NLRP12 expression was repressed by following MDP sensing in healthy human monocytes. In HEK293, weak induction of NLRP12 following MDP sensing in cells expressing wild-type human NOD2 was significantly reduced in cells expressing Crohn's Disease mutant NOD2 L1007P.